

Four-dimensional plasma lipidomics in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma reveals many differentially expressed lipids

David Pirić¹, Vesna Vasić², Zorica Cvetković³, Romana Masnikosa¹

¹ Department of Physical Chemistry, Institute of Nuclear Sciences Vinča, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

² Gimnazija Ruđer Bošković, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

³ Medical Faculty, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

Diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) is the predominant type of non-Hodgkin lymphoma, the most common haematological malignancy¹. Global plasma lipidomic status almost invariably alters in malignancies² and there is no data for plasma lipidome in DLBCL. We conducted an untargeted plasma lipidomic study in 17 female DLBCL patients and 21 healthy females, employing a novel 4D lipidomics workflow³, in which lipid species were identified by their RP-UPLC retention time, accurate m/z measurement, MS/MS spectra and collisional cross-section values derived from trapped ion mobility spectrometry. Using the class-specific internal standards, we quantified 267 lipid species. Univariate statistics and fold change (ratio of average lipid concentration in DLBCL vs. control group, FC) revealed differentially expressed lipids (DELs) in the two studied groups. To distinguish the groups, we built an OPLS DA model, extracted the major lipid features that contributed to the model and computed their VIP (variable of importance) values. The most profoundly DELs in DLBCL were decided according to the rule: p-value < 0.05, FC > 1.4 or < 0.6, and VIP > 1.5, as following: (lyso)phosphatidylcholines: PC 18:2_18:2, LPC 18:2/0:0, LPC 0:0/18:2, LPC 22:0/0:0; ether-linked PCs: PC O-34:0, PC O-34:2, PC O-34:3, lysophosphatidylethanolamine LPE 0:0/18:2; ether-linked: PE O-16:1_18:2, PE O-17:1_18:2; phosphatidylinositols: PI 18:0_18:1, PI 18:1_18:2; phosphatidylserine PS 18:0_20:4; sphingomyelins: SM d31:1, SM d36:0, SM d44:1; ceramides: Cer d18:1_24:0, Cer d18:1_24:1, Cer d44:1 and diglycerides: DG 16:0_18:1, DG 18:1_18:2. This lipid panel might contain candidate lipid signatures of DLBCL, but it should be confirmed in independent studies on larger number of cases.

Corresponding Author:

David Pirić

Doctoral student

Department of Physical Chemistry, Institute of Nuclear Sciences, University of Belgrade

Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14, 11000 Belgrade, Republic of Serbia

david.piric@vin.bg.ac.rs

phone: +381654124735

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